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Entry	IRRI						PhilRice				
	Vegetative stage		Reproductive stage				Vegetative stage		Reproductive stage		
	Tillers (no.)	% DH ^b	Productive tillers (no.)	% WH ^b	% SSB ^{c,d}	Silica content (%)	Tillers (no.)	% DH ^b	Productive tillers (no.)	% WH ^b	% SSB ^{b,d}
IR67962-84-2-2	10.6	11.2 (19.5)	5.9	28.4 (32.1)	99.0 (10.0)	5.9	15.2	27.7 (31.6)	7.4	35.9 (36.8)	69.9 (57.0)
IR62	15.0	5.7 (13.6)	20.6	17.7 (24.8)	79.2 (8.9)	6.3	27.2	19.7 (26.0)	26.9	27.8 (31.7)	42.5 (40.4)
IR64	17.6	10.8 (18.9)	20.6	107 (19.0)	76.3 (8.7)	6.4	21.9	17.8 (24.6)	21.8	13.5 (21.5)	36.4 (36.7)
IR72	13.9	7.0 (15.2)	11.7	16.1 (23.6)	92.1 (9.6)	6.2	29.2	10.1 (17.8)	25.7	17.1 (24.3)	53.5 (46.5)
LSD (0.05)	2.3	5.7	2.3	6.3	0.4	n.s	3.3	5.1	2.3	7.2	14.1
LSD (0.01)	3.0	7.5	3.0	8.3	0.5		4.3	6.8	3.1	9.5	18.7

^aDH = deadhearts, WH = whiteheads. ^bNumbers in parentheses are arcsine-square root-transformed means. ^cNumbers in parentheses are square root-transformed means. ^d% of larvae and pupae in dissected plants infested with SSB.

Effects of simulated pest damage on rice yields

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The types and levels of damage affecting rice yields at different crop stages were evaluated by simulating pest damage. Many plant species have the ability to decrease the negative effects of injury on yield, a process known as compensation (Pedigo 1991). Rice can compensate for stem borer damage at the tillering stage (Rubia 1994). Rice plants, however, do not compensate for cut tillers to the same degree that they compensate for stem borer damage (Rubia 1996).

Four damage simulation trials were conducted from February 1998 to January 1999 in Phnom Penh, Cambodia, using a randomized complete block design with four replications and four treatments per replicate. Each replicate consisted of a concrete basin (2.8 m × 2.4 m surface, 0.6 m deep), filled with soil to a depth of 0.4 m. The NPK rate was the same in all experiments—60-60-30 kg ha⁻¹, applied as 30-30-30 NPK basally and 30-30 NP at panicle initiation (PI). There were 30 seedlings treatment⁻¹ (1 seedling hill⁻¹) at 20-cm spacing. IR66 seedlings (25 d old) and medium-duration CAR11 seedlings (33 d old)

were transplanted. In these experiments, “50% damage” refers to complete removal of half of the leaves or stems, not cutting the leaves or stems in half. The weight and moisture content of each plot’s yield were recorded. Weights were adjusted to 14% moisture and converted to t ha⁻¹. Significant differences in mean treatment yields were detected by ANOVA and LSD with IRRISTAT 4.0.

Removing all of the leaves from seedlings and cutting off 50% of the leaves at tillering did not significantly reduce yields of IR66. Cutting off 50% of the leaves at booting significantly reduced yields. Cutting off 50% of tillers at booting significantly reduced yields of IR66. Cutting off 50% of tillers at stem elongation, however, did not significantly reduce yields. LSD analysis produced an inconclusive result for treatments with all seedlings cut off at water level. Cutting off 100% of stems at the seedling, tillering, or booting stage of IR66 resulted in yields significantly lower than those of undamaged controls. No IR66 seedlings recovered from cutting at ground level in standing water (Table 1).

Cutting off all seedlings at ground level, cutting off all tillers 30 d after transplanting (DAT) at the water surface, and cutting off all tillers at booting at water level significantly reduced yields of CAR11, although some plants showed vegetative recovery (Table 2). Unlike IR66, CAR11 seedlings exhibited some recovery from cutting at ground level in standing water.

The yields in these experiments are typically achieved by Cambodian rice farmers. These results suggest that rice has a considerable capacity to compensate for or recover from drastic damage. Removing all leaves during the seedling stage and 50% of leaves during stem elongation did not reduce yields, while removing 50% of leaves at booting did. A leaf damage of more than 50% by pests is quite rare. This suggests that, before PI, it may not be necessary to manage pests of rainfed rice, which restrict their damage to leaves, except to lower pest density and reduce damage at PI. Likewise, pests that cut tillers such as rats (Jahn et al 1999) are more likely to reduce yields after PI.

Table 1. Yield response of IR66 to simulated pest damage at different crop stages.

Treatment	Mean yield (t ha ⁻¹)	F	PROB	5% LSD
Cut off all seedling leaves	3.1	3.91*	0.04	0.467
Cut off 50% of leaves at tillering	3.2			
Cut off 50% of leaves at booting	2.6			
Control for trial no. 1	3.3			
Cut off all seedlings at water level	2.8	5.19*	0.02	0.518
Cut off 50% of tillers at stem elongation	3.1			
Cut off 50% of tillers at booting	2.5			
Control for trial no. 2	3.3			
Cut off all seedlings at ground level	0	78.43**	0.001	0.485
Cut off all tillers 30 DAT at water level	1.5			
Cut off all tillers at booting at water level	0.5			
Control for trial no. 3	3.0			

* = significantly different at 0.05% level, ** = significantly different at 0.01% level, PROB = probability.

Table 2. Yield response of CAR11 to complete stem-cutting at different crop stages.

Treatment	Mean yield (t ha ⁻¹)	F	PROB	5% LSD
Cut off all seedlings at ground level	1.2	38.47**	0.001	0.786
Cut off all tillers 30 DAT at water level	2.8			
Cut off all tillers at booting at water level	0.4			
Control	3.8			

** = significantly different at 0.01% level, PROB = probability.

Even before PI, extensive rat damage could reduce yields, as indicated by the observation that cutting 50% of tillers at stem elongation did not reduce yields, but cutting all tillers at 30 DAT reduced yields.

Crabs and snails (Jahn et al 1998), which cut off seedlings at ground level, are expected to reduce yields of early or medium-maturing varieties. Armyworms, cutworms, and some grasshopper species

destroy rice plants down to the water level, which could suppress yields if damage were done at booting, though not necessarily at the seedling stage. Cutting off 50% of tillers at stem elongation did not reduce yields of IR66, suggesting that it could tolerate rat damage up to at least 50% tiller cut (per plant, not per field) before PI.

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